
360 Radio Experience: Connecting Live Listening with User Interaction and Visual Radio

Sandy Claes
Sebastiaan Jansen
VRT innovation
Brussels
sandy.claes@vrt.be

Sebastiaan.jansen@vrt.be

ABSTRACT

Today, radio stations connect the live listening experience to interaction with their listeners through social and other media, such as own applications that offer unique experiences tailored to their needs. VRT, public broadcaster of Flanders in Belgium is currently studying how to streamline all these interactions into a simple editorial workflow. This way, the editorial team is able to handle these increasing points of interaction with radio stations (e.g. by leveraging smart automations). In this paper, we present a case study of 'Music for Life'; a large-scale charity of VRT's radio station Studio Brussel that spans 4 months and is concluded with a week-long live radio show. In this case we studied the use of a chatbot to handle the incoming listener messages, including text, photo and video content, and present the results. We then conclude this position paper by describing two opportunities to deploy the user generated content that is triggered by radio producers for supporting the live experience of radio.

KEYWORDS

Radio; visual radio; user generated content; user experience

INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

Today, radio consumption is allowed via diverse output devices, such as smartphone devices, DAB+ slideshow support, a dedicated TV channel for radio, etc. besides traditional radio devices. These devices offer a range of opportunities for interaction with the radio station, which go beyond the traditional approach of listeners that call into the radio show by telephone or send in text messages [4], such as polls via Instagram, moderated competitions via the radio station's dedicated smartphone application or mobile radio studios that can be set up closer to their audience (e.g. at a sports event). Radio has always been perceived as a *'friend that is present in the background'* yet the interactive possibilities have even provided opportunities to tighten that relationship [5]. Indeed, via these interactive devices, listeners are increasingly responding to and conversating with radio producers. For instance, listeners share their live music experiences by sending photographic materials or even video footage of concerts or festivals to radio station spontaneously [3], resulting in large sets of user generated content at the radio stations' side. On the other hand, to trigger interaction, radio producers increasingly communicate visual materials (e.g. photos, gifs, memes) via social media to support dialogues with their audience 'off-air'. As a result, there is an opportunity to explore the potential of 'user generated visual radio', i.e. supporting the live experience of radio listening through visual materials that are triggered by radio producers and created by its listeners.

More specifically, in this position paper we will explore the potential of such user generated content for visual radio. For several years now, radio stations broadcast a live webcam stream on television and on their websites. Visually, we recognize the radio studio, which is mostly a static environment; a banner is placed in the background, and three or more displays face the radio presenter. Radio presenters reported they feel they produce better radio when they are able to see and interact with their listeners, e.g. in the context of a live event [1]. In fact, in that study, radio producers imagined displays in the radio studio to be able to provide an overview of listeners' activities, which would support their feeling of better radio production [1]. Here, we recognize the potential of user generated photos or videos as a constant stream that can support the live experience of radio.

In this paper, we will explore those opportunities in the context of our work at VRT (i.e. the public broadcaster of the Flanders region in Belgium). Here, we are currently investigating and developing a platform that allows radio producers to manage listener interactions that are facilitated via social media (i.e. Twitter, Facebook, Instagram) or via our radio stations' smartphone applications [6]. In particular, we focused on developing an editorial tool for radio producers that allows to search in the incoming messages of listeners, which can then be added in the rundown to be used during the show. The editorial interface is also used to configure a chatbot application in which newly produced automatic answers and dialog flows are added and trained. As such, we support radio producers to focus on the actual interactions with their listeners.

Figure 1. Screenshot of live broadcast television during Music for Life, in which user generated photos of a listener activity are displayed on the right, user generated text is shown in the blue line below, and an overview of present listeners at the charity event location in the background.

Figure 2. Screenshot of the live broadcast television of Music for Life in which the remote radio studio and the radio presenter are shown in the background and a user generated video is shown in the plywood frame in the front right.

These applications and tools are evaluated in-the-wild [6], in the actual radio studios of VRT during live radio shows. In particular for user generated visual materials, we connected our evaluation to 'Music for Life'; a large-scale charity of VRT's radio station Studio Brussel that spans 4 months and is concluded with a week-long live radio show that is aired from a remote studio on an event location in the end of December [8].

Case study – Music for Life

In the 14 weeks leading up to the charity event, listeners can sign up to host an activity to collect funds for a good cause, such as a bake sale or a sports game. Often, these 'listener-organizers' have many questions about how they should host the activity, how they should deliver the collected money, if they can tell their story live on radio, and so on. The radio production team, on the other hand, also have many questions for those listener-organizer: if they have footage of their event to share, what the current financial balance of their campaign is, etc. Answering these questions manually is time consuming, therefore, we deployed our chatbot in this case study. During the total span of the charity event, the chatbot was used by 1.908 people who sent a total of 24.615 messages. Only 9% of those messages were not understood by the chatbot and were forwarded to conversation team who handled them personally. Most of the messages that were not understood were simple updates on the activities supported by the listener-organizers, such as "We already raised 1.000 Euro" or comments on videos and pictures they had send and did not require any answer. Semi-structured interviews with 3 radio producers revealed how the chatbot relieved their work in answering repetitive or generic questions.

Most of the incoming messages were photos (N= 15.234), then text (N= 7.788) and videos (N=1.593). To process that user generated content, the editorial team controlled the appropriateness of the incoming messages, images and video's and approves. This process still required intensive manual labor of the radio producers. When a photo or video is then approved, it is automatically sent to a queue to be shown on the live television broadcast during the week-long charity event, and on digital displays at the event location.

Indeed, surrounding the remote studio, there is a large visitor area where listener-organizers are able to hand over the funds they raised and request a song. As this studio and experience is built from the ground up for this occasion, it serves as an ideal testbed for studies with the studio arrangement. Also, this studio is equipped with displays and cameras as it is broadcasted live on television. Specifically, one dedicated display in the remote radio studio

showcased photos sent in by listener-organizers. In the visitor area, also beacons were installed to sense when and how many listener-organizers were present (i.e. as they have a dedicated application for the charity event, which tracks their location with their consent). This presence was also linked to the displays as it presented their content when in vicinity of the displays. We expected listener-organizers to further engage and send new photos when they notice those photos are displayed in the area, or, in general, attract non-engaged listeners to deliver user generated content. More than 75.000 people visited the event location, of which the beacons identified 278 listener-organizers.

OPPORTUNITIES

Based on our studies in Music for Life, we identify two opportunities to be further explored in the context of visual radio that builds upon user generated content.

The integration of visual content analysis to allow radio producers to search user generated visual materials. The chatbot application caused the radio producers to work more efficiently and focused on relevant questions and interesting stories as they were relieved from repetitive questions and responses. However, most incoming messages were photos, still requiring many efforts of the radio production team to interpret, check and approve or disapprove content. In future, we aim to expand our tool with visual analysis that allow to search the visual materials. As a result, radio producers will be relieved from generic interpretation tasks to enable them to focus on the actual storytelling process that can be supported by user generated content. For instance, instead of communicating listener activities separately, they might connect activities that are similar in one coherent 'story'. In that respect, because of the low threshold for interaction and its characteristic of being 'live' in the moment, radio might provide an interesting testbed for professional, on the fly storytelling with user generated content, which may result into lessons for television production.

Automatically select and present user generated content on studio displays. Stories that are made with user generated content already require some form of processing by a (radio) producer. However, we also see an opportunity to embed appropriate user generated visual materials in a constant stream on the studio displays, thereby providing a rich overview of listeners' activities for the radio presenters and producers and supporting the live experience. At Music for Life, the (sometimes) poor visual quality of user generated photos were compensated by displaying photos and videos in a subsection of the full resolution broadcast (see Figure 2). Here, we will further investigate how the quality of user generated content can be enhanced automatically, e.g. by incorporating the tools created in [7].

CONCLUSION

In this position paper we explored opportunities to deploy the user generated content that is triggered by radio producers for supporting the live experience of radio. We presented a case study on collecting user generated content in the context of a charity event that is set up by a radio station. In this study, listeners are enabled to send content concerning their contributions to the charity event, resulting into a rich data set, mostly consisting of photographic materials. We identify two opportunities to further exploit that materials, i.e. (1) allowing radio producers to also search visual content and (2) integrating user generated content streams in the radio studios to connect radio presenters with listeners.

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